

A Sociological Survey on the Socio-Economic Status of Elderly Widows in Garadaha Village of West Bengal

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Abstract

Women in Indian society from time immemorial remained the victim of humiliation, exploitation and subjugation. This situation becomes worse with the increasing age of the women. Aged women after 60+ suffers crisis, mentally, economically and socially. The researcher concentrates her study in certain rural areas of Durgapur sub-division in Burdwan District and purposively selected 30 elderly widows as her respondents. Through intensive interview, the researcher purports to study the existing socio-economic problems of the respondents in rural settings. It was found out that most of the respondents are suffering from extreme economic crisis, social isolation and severe health problems. It is also surprisingly noticed that no local NGO or voluntary organisation are providing any supportive assistance to them, leaving them alone to face severe distress in their remaining life span. Active social work intervention is required to minimise the adverseness of the existing situation.

Key words: Changing demography of aged women, dependency on others, problems of aged women of rural areas, poverty and widowhood, NGO, Social Work Intervention.

Introduction

Widowhood is a critical and hard period in a woman's life. It is a much more significant and pressing problem than divorce. In addition to bereavement it also means re-adjusting to a new social situation.

Widowhood may have deleterious effects not only because of the sudden loss of the spouse but also because of the lack of well defined cultural expectations regarding the role of the widow.

It also had social consequences both for members of immediate family and the wider community. This often has a damaging effect on the "self concept" of a widow. The extent and duration of this damage are affected by the intensity of involvement with the departed spouse and the availability of alternative "significant other" (Bankoff, 1983).

From the sociological point of view, widowhood may be understood as a change in the status of women brought about by the death of spouse in a marital dyad and which necessitates the establishment of new relations within the family, with the kin group and with community (Marris, 1958). Widowhood brings about severe social, economic, emotional and cultural deprivation. It is the last stage of a family life cycle and mostly it is associated with old age. Generally, it is considered since the ancient times that woman has no individual entity of her own in this world (Berado, 1967). According to Simone de Beauvoir, Man Occupies the role of the self, or subject; women is the object, the other. A woman in Indian society has been victim of humiliation, torture and exploitation. Indian society is pre-dominated by men; hence women are a victim of male domination in the respective sphere of life, especially in economic life. Man, as father, brother, or husband, or son, considers women as socio-economic gift of his household. A woman's value is judged, not so much in terms of her worth as a person with rights and dignity as in terms of her utility to man. According to Hindu Shastras, widows should remain stable like a stone and she should stay in-door and think of God, only then she can keep her husband always alive in her mind even after his death and always think of the welfare of the children. Women, be it daughter, wife, sister, or old mother are always controlled

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and dominated by the patriarchal social order (Ghosh, 1982).

Widowhood is crisis in a women's life involving new social adjustment for the family as well as for her. It is an event that constitutes the greatest and saddest change in the life of a woman. It is rightly said that widowhood at all ages, changes the basic self identity of many women. This is especially true of traditionally oriented women in India where the role of wife is to maintain control over their lives (Nagesh & Nair, 1988).

According to Greg, Widowhood is an event that brings about the greatest change in the status of women, this is not only because of the loss of the husband, but also because of the lack of clear cut cultural expectations regarding the proper role of the widow (Mishra, 1987).

Magnitude of elderly population in India with special reference to elderly widows

In the 20th century, the proportion of population aged 60 or over has increased in all the countries of the world. About 600 million people in the world were aged 60 or over at the turn of the new millennium and their numbers are expected to increase further due to substantial improvement in life expectancy throughout the world. This is particularly due to improvement in public health and medical awareness in the prevention of many deadly epidemic diseases. This, together with steadily declining birth rate and fertility trends, lead to increase in the share of the aged in total population in India (Central Statistics Office, 2011).

India currently has around a 104 million older people that constitute 9% of the total population (Census of India: SRS Bulletin, 2011). The proportion of India's older population is projected to increase to 18.3% by 2050 and cross 30% by 2100 (United Nations, 2002). The decadal growth rate for the older population in India during 1991-2001 was 40% i.e. almost double the growth rate of general population i.e. 21%. India alone will house 15.8% i.e. 323 million of the total older population of the world by 2050.

Percentage Distribution of population by Broad Age Group in India since 1991

Year	Age Groups		
	0-14	15-59	60+
1991	37.6	55.7	6.7
2001	35.3	56.9	7.4
2011*	29.0	62.7	8.2
2021*	25.1	64.0	10.7

*Projected figures
Source- Population Census data for the period 1991-2001

Percentage share of elderly population (aged 60 years and above) in total population

Source	Person	Female	Male	Rural	Urban
Census 1961	5.6	5.8	5.5	5.8	4.7
Census 1971	6.0	6.0	5.9	6.2	5.0
Census 1981	6.5	6.6	6.4	6.8	5.4
Census 1991	6.8	6.8	6.7	7.1	5.7
Census 2001	7.4	7.8	7.1	7.7	6.7
NSSO Survey (2004-05)	7.2	7.5	6.9	7.3	7.0
NSSO Survey (2007-08)	7.5	7.7	7.3	7.6	7.2

There has been a steady rise in the share of elderly population in the total population over the decades. As against 5.6% in 1961, the proportion goes up to 7.4% in 2001 and up to 8% in 2011. For males, the rise was more modest from 5.5% to 7.1% and to 7.7% in 2011, while for females, there had been a steep rise from 5.8% to 7.8% and to 8.4% in 2011 during the six decadal censuses from 1961 to 2011 (Mari Bhat, 1992). Among the States, the proportion of elderly in total population vary from around 6% in small states, like Delhi, Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, to more than 8% in Andhra Pradesh (8.8%), Gujrat (8.3%), Jammu & Kashmir (8.4%), Karnataka (8.4%), West Bengal (8.2%),

Maharashtra (9.3%), Punjab (9.5%) and in Kerala (12.6%) according to Census, 2011 (Census of India: SRS Bulletin, 2011).

The sex ratio among elderly population was as high as 1000 in 1951 but subsequently dropped to about 938 in 1971 but has finally increased again to about 972 in 2001. It is also noticed that there is relatively higher ratio of females to males in the elderly population than in the general population for all the years since Independence.

Trends in Sex Ratio (No. of Females per 1000 males) for elderly and the general population

Population Census	Elderly Population	General Population
1961	1000	941
1971	938	930
1981	960	934
1991	930	927
2001	972	933
2011	*	940

*Not yet declared

Source- Population Census data up to year 2001

The phenomenon of "Feminisation of Aging" is evident in India since 2001 as reflected by Census 2001. There was only 7.1% older males as compared to 7.8% female older when the data on older was disaggregated by gender. Census 2011 also reveals similar findings where older women outnumber older men by 7.1 million. In 2012, for every 100 women aged 60, there were only 92 men in India and the proportion of women rises further with age. For every 100 women aged 80 or over worldwide, there are only 82 men (Census of India, 2001). The decadal growth rate of older women is 42.2 as compared to 28.6 in older males, which points towards the rapidly increasing proportion of older women in India.

Problems of elderly widows in India

In India with majority of its population aged less than 30, the problems and issues of its grey population has not been given serious consideration and only a few studies on them have been attempted in our country. However, with the rapid changes in the social scenario and the emerging prevalence of nuclear family set-ups in

India in recent years, the elderly people are likely to be exposed to emotional, physical and financial insecurity in the years to come. Ageing of population is affected due to downward trends in fertility and mortality. Low birth rates coupled with long expectancies, push the population to an ageing humanity (Dreze & Srinivasan, 1998).

It is observed that percentage of aged 60 or more is rapidly swelling and even the percentage of persons above age 80 is going up over the years. Simultaneously, the ratio of people of "working age" (15-59years) to those of elderly population is shrinking. Hence the dependency ratio is increasing and the problems faced by the females are more critical compared to that of men due to low literacy rate, customary ownership of property by men and majority of women being not in labour force during their prime age with only very few in the organized sector (Irudaya, Rajan, Mishra, & Sarma, 2003).

It is observed specially in India, that Hindu women regards widowhood as a punishment for some horrible crimes committed by them in their previous birth such as disobedience or disloyalty to their husband etc. Widowhood and its accompanying miserable existence, is considered as atonement for some sin committed in their previous birth. Widowhood marks a transition from a marital status to a widowed status which is not smooth, for it means not only a loss of pride, privileges, prestige, independence within a family, but also it means addition difficulty in adjustment to be made (Prasad, 1991). A woman's life becomes more miserable in absence of husband, especially in Indian society. For a man, the loss of spouse is considered as a personal grief but for a woman is something more than that. Women, generally in their old age, faces more difficulty in making adjustment with this new status because of the social norms and taboos puts her in utmost disadvantaged position (Chen, 2000). Hence it was realised that every phase of widowhood is critical hard, challenging and demanding which brings about severe social, economical, emotional and cultural deprivation in the life of the woman. For the elderly population (above 60+ age group), widowhood is a critical situation which involves both social and personal disorganization. The

seriousness of the problem and its degree varies with the widow's age, economic conditions, education, caste, family structure, religion, norms and others. For the elderly widows, change in socio-economic status and various health problems adversely affect their life (Bose & Sen, 1965).

Rationale of the study

The importance of study of widowhood lies in the fact that the death of the married person in a family brings about a number of economic and social changes especially in the life of his/her spouse and children. The changes would be larger and serious in case of death among middle aged persons who had much dependence especially spouse and young children.

When the question of condition/problems of old widows/widowers; is considered it is observed that widows and widowers are given less recognition in the society than others. Looking at different angles as above, we can understand that widowhood has substantial socio-economic which not to be explored in depth.

The researcher purports to explore the socio-economic conditions of elderly widows of rural areas which seem to suffer more in comparison to the widows of urban areas. Hence it is essential to understand the factors affecting adversely their problems.

Statement of the problem

Women as a whole in India face various deprivations and issues during their life course, due to its socio-cultural context as well as gender roles. Low literacy, low participation in paid employment, poor access to assets, poor nutrition and ill health coverage among older women who belong to poor families and communities and these render them poorly equipped to deal with a multitude of deprivations. The socio-economic implications of ageing are greater for females because of their higher life expectancy. An important issue requiring both research and policy attention is the interdependence among women's

economic, health and social concerns which increase with age.

Surprisingly little is known about the actual lives of rural aged widows in India either currently or historically. Very few studies have focused on widows as a distinct social group and attempted to provide a comprehensive analysis of their social and economical condition in contemporary India.

The present study deals mainly with the various problems faced by aged widow in traditional Hindu society, as well as the socio-economic and demographic implications of widowhood. The main focus of the study deals with the problems faced by aged widows residing in rural Durgapur, the factors responsible for the present study is to investigate the circumstances.

Objectives of the study

- The study of the changes brought about by widowhood in the socio- economic conditions of widows.
- To ascertain the difficulties faced by the widows especially in their old age and the reason responsible for the same.

Methodology of the Study

The researcher followed exploratory research design and with the help of semi-structured interview schedule collected data from 30 aged women who are widow. The researcher conducted the study in certain selected rural areas of Durgapur namely Garadaha and Domra under Trilokchandrapur Gram Panchayet, Kanksa Block under Burdwan district and approached 30 aged (60+) widowed women and interviewed them with the help of purposive sampling technique. In-depth interview was taken from 30 respondents individually to obtain rich source of information in order to achieve a more comprehensive insight about the research problem. Apart from personal interviews, the researcher also collected some information from secondary sources like Government reports, books, journals etc. The information collected from various categories of respondents is tabulated and analysis was done with the help of simple statistics.

46-50	4	13.33
51-60	10	33.33
Total	30	100.00

Analysis of Data

Table No. 1 (Distribution of Elderly Widow by Age)

Age Distribution(yrs)	Number Respondents	Percentage
60-69	15	50
70-79	11	36.67
80 and above	4	13.33
Total	30	100.00

Table No. 2 (Educational level)

Educational level	Number Respondent	Percentage
Illiterate	8	26.67
Neo- literate	15	16.67
Primary	13	43.33
Secondary and above	4	13.33
total	30	100.00

Table No. 3 (Age at Widowhood of the Elderly widows)

Age at widowhood(years)	Number of respondents	Percentage
35-40	3	10
41-45	13	44.33

Table No. 4 (Participation in Religious Activities)

Age at widowhood(year)	Number of respondents	Percentage
35-40	3	10
41-45	13	44.33
46-50	4	13.33
51-60	10	33.33
Total	30	100.00

Table No. 5 (Spends leisure time)

Spending leisure time	Number of respondents	Percentage
Watching TV	9	30.00
Listening Radio	4	13.33
Playing with grand children	11	36.67
Gossiping with neighbours and family members	6	20.00
Total	30	100.00

Table No.6 (Major illnesses they suffer)

Major illness	Number of respondents	Percentage
Blood pressure and heart problems	12	40.00

Sugar	7	22.33
T.B.	2	6.66
Depression	1	3.33
Neuro problems	4	13.33
Gastro problems	2	6.67
Breathing problem	1	3.33
No major illness	1	3.33
Total	30	100.00

Figure No. 7 (Change in food habits after widowhood)

Changes observed in food habit	Number of respondents	Percentage
Turn into vegetarian after the death of their husbands	22	73.33
No change	8	26.67
Total	30	100.00

Table -8 (Participation and decision making process)

Participation and decision making process	Number of respondents	Percentage
Participate	14	46.67
No participation	16	53.33
Total	30	100.00

Table No. 9 (Monthly income of the respondents)

Income of elderly widows	Number of respondents	Percent
Five thousand and above	3	10.00

Up to five thousand	19	63.33
No income	8	26.66
Total	30	100.00

Table -10 (Source of monthly income of Elderly Widows)

Source of income of elderly widow	Number of respondents	Percentage
Bank interest	10	33.33
Agriculture	9	30.00
Widow pension scheme	11	36.67
Total	30	100.00

Table No. 11 (Property left by the deceased husband)

Property left by the husband	Number of respondents	Percentage
Inherited property	22	73.33
No property	8	26.67
Total	30	100.00

Table -12 (Economic difficulties faced by the respondents)

Economic difficulty	Number of respondents	Percentage
Face economic difficulty	18	60.00
Do not face	12	40.00
Total	30	100.00

Table-13 (Assistance receive to overcome economic difficulty)

Assistance receive to overcome economic difficulty	Number of respondents	Percentage
Sons	12	40.00
Sons and daughters	14	46.67
Relatives	4	13.33
Total	30	100.00

Discussion of the findings

Discussing about the results, it can be highlighted that most of the respondents who are elderly widows are belonging to the age group of (60-69) years, i.e. (50%), but irrespective of age group, elderly women have given their diversified views. Most of the women are not much educated, i.e. maximum respondents are having primary level of education (43.33%) and 26.67% are illiterate. But surprisingly, the respondents have given different views irrespective of their educational level. This is also seen that most of the respondents had became widow before 50 years of age so it can be said that on the one hand, they are poor and downtrodden women and on the other hand they are left alone by their husband in the path of economic hardships. It is also seen from the results that most of the respondents have participated in religious activities quite frequently. This is a natural trend among the women to participate in various religious activities especially in middle age and it is not unlikely that the poor women at their widowhood and in old age, more and more becomes involved in religious

activities. Apart from participating in religious activities, the aged widows spend their leisure time in several ways like watching television (30%), playing with grand children (36.67%). Apart from this, they listen to radio (13.33%) and sometimes gossip with neighbour and family members. The widows in their old age suffer from various illnesses like more likely from blood pressure and heart problems (30%), blood sugar (22.33%), and neuro-problems (13.35%). As the respondents are Bengali speaking women, so it is customary and traditional practice to restrict oneself from eating non vegetarian food after the demise of their husbands (73.33%) and only 8 women out of 30 have not changed their eating habit after widowhood.

The researcher found a very mixed response from the respondents regarding their participation in family decision making process. Most of the respondents stay with their son's family and some respondents usually participate in the family decisions (46.67%) again 53.33% of them said they are just staying with the family, (either with son or else), but they never participate in their family decision neither they are asked to do so.

This is very unfortunate that 26.66% of the respondents are having no income and they are completely dependent on their relative's income which makes their life most distressful. In comparison to that other 73.33% who are having a standard income from different sources are more comfortable and are ready to face all atrocities in their life. They get their income from several sources like Bank interest (33.33%); agricultural field (30%) and a certain number of respondents get widow pension scheme (36.67%).

As already mentioned earlier, 73.33% of the women have stable income from different sources, it is also ascertained that they inherit property from their husbands. Most of the respondents face economic difficulty due to meagre income and uncertainty and delayed process of getting their monthly instalments (60%). This is also very surprising to notice that discussing about the assistance they receive to overcome economic difficulty, no NGO or

voluntary organisation is involving to provide any support to this distressed poor aged women. Most of them are getting assistance from their sons (40%); sons & daughters (46.67%) and sometimes from relatives (13.33%).

Conclusions

The problems of elderly widows are related to the general position of women and socio-economic conditions in the country. Unless the status of women in general is not raised and the socio-economic conditions are not substantively improved, the plight of elderly widows will remain more or less the same.

With the decline in fertility and mortality rates accompanied by an improvement in child survival and increased life expectancy, a significant feature of demographic change is the progressive increase in the number of elderly persons. Increasing life span and poor health care add to the degree of disability among the elderly and compound the problems of care giving. In India, the life expectancy has steadily gone up from 32 years at the time of independence to over 63 in 2001. The elderly experience changes in different aspects of their lives.

With rapid increase in elderly population accompanied by a decline in the physiological functions in this age group, the foremost apparent challenge is to prevent physiological ageing getting converted into pathological ageing i.e. when diseases supervene. The psychosocial environment around elderly is also to be kept healthy.

The care of the elderly is drawing more and more attention of the Government and public. It is already a major social and health problem in affluent countries. While science has prolonged life, the changes that it has brought about in cultural and social patterns have robbed the elderly of their status and self-esteem and have deprived them of chance to function adequately in the society.

Majority of the problems that confront older persons are the result of priorities, policies and practices of society. Ageing is mainly associated with social isolation, poverty, apparent

reduction in family support, inadequate housing, impairment of cognitive functioning, mental illness, widowhood, loss, bereavement, limited options for living arrangement and dependency towards end of life.

All these problems have an impact on the quality of life in old age and health care at the time of need. In traditional Indian societies, joint family system used to take care of most of these social issues. However, with industrialization and urbanization, disintegration of traditional joint family has been the major social problem. Nevertheless family and the community is the most important caretaker of elderly in India. It is thus necessary to strengthen the traditional family system through community education and social intervention.

In the absence of well-organized social support network, the scenario appears gloomy. In not so distant future, the elderly in the organized sector will be opting more and more for living arrangement namely old age homes and senior citizen homes. For the elderly in the unorganized sector the options remain limited to poverty and destitution, in absence of family support.

Particular problems of adjustment are associated with ageing, but these problems are caused accompanying the ageing process than by the fact that the person has aged. Among the more stressful experiences affecting a person's outlook and expectations during older adulthood are changes in physical appearances and cognitive abilities, chronic illness, financial difficulties, loss of status and roles, isolation through disease or disability and the deaths of relatives and friends. Physical changes in old age are especially difficult to cope with because the appearances and perception of one's own body can have a profound effect on the self-concept.

Older and younger people alike tend to minimize their physical and mental limitations and disabilities, a response that is normal and self-protective. Most people do not like to think of themselves as ageing or disabled, because such thoughts are likely to produce feelings of discomfort and anxiety. But everyone ages, and

ageing can affect personality and the ability to adjust to the physical and social environment. Furthermore, because the body and mind operate as a psycho-somatic unit, the level of adjustment and mental health can influence the rate at which a person ages. According to Erikson, the major crisis of old age is integrity versus despair and the primary goal is to become an integrated and self-accepting person. How the individual handles this crisis depends on personality characteristics that have been developing for years, as well as physical health, economic situation and the meaningfulness of the social roles that can be played successfully.

Recommendations

The following suggestions for improving the conditions of widowed elderly women are offered.

- Community education is a much needed service, as far as changes towards widows are concerns.
- Voluntary organizations, Professional social workers can play a significant role in the area of community education in this regard.
- It is suggested that widows under indigent circumstances should be given reasonable attention.
- A wide publicity of government schemes for the elderly should be made through mass media.
- It is essential to carry out the field studies in all communities regarding the condition of elderly widows to understand what elderly widows expect from society and how the society can fulfil those expectations.
- The programmes emphasizing the need for change in the socio religious attitudes of the people elderly widows should be adopted.
- Social stigma attached to the widowhood had to be removed through social and economic programmes.
- Elderly widows should be encouraged to participate in various ceremonies

or rituals whenever opportunity presents itself.

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